

Evaluation of Cochlear Slice Finite-Element Models to Simulate 3D Organ of Corti Tissue Mechanics

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Abstract. The micromechanics of the cochlear organ of Corti (OoC) is fundamental to the ability to hear but is insufficiently understood. Current work examines a proposed finite-element (FE) modeling technique that captures the 3-dimensional motion of the OoC under the influence of the passive traveling wave. The proposed modeling technique takes a thin slice of the cochlea to make computation feasible to include the OoC tissue. The application of Floquet boundary condition considers the effect of the traveling wave. The results show that the slice FE modeling technique is promising for capturing the motion of the OoC in all 3 dimensions.

INTRODUCTION

The organ of Corti (OoC) is anatomically and mechanically intricate that transduces the mechanical motions of the traveling wave to auditory nerve impulses. The intricacy of the OoC structure not only lies in the transverse and radial directions of positions of inner hair cells (IHCs) and outer hair cells (OHCs) and overlaying tectorial membrane, but also in the longitudinal inclination of the OHCs, Deiters' cells (DCs), and phalangeal processes (PhPs). Exactly how the different structures within the OoC move together and relative to each other with the traveling wave remain elusive despite significant efforts in trying to understand the micromechanics of OoC experimentally¹⁻⁵. Recent advances in Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT)^{1,5-7} and other imaging techniques^{2,3} provided fertile ground for furthering our understanding in this area. Modeling is also abundant in trying to understand the stimulation mechanism of IHCs bundles and the amplification mechanism⁸⁻¹⁰.

It has been proposed to use a 3-dimensional (3D) finite element (FE) model with a thin slice of the cochlea to study the micromechanics of the OoC using Floquet boundary condition (BC)^{10,11} at the longitudinal faces that takes into account the effect of the traveling wave in the BM and OoC on the micromechanics of OoC. These slice models can include the 3D details of the OoC with solutions that are computationally efficient in comparison to full-length cochlear models where incorporation of such details is not computationally feasible. The goal of the current work was to evaluate the accuracy and limitations of the slice modeling technique with a Floquet boundary condition using the method to simulate the BM and OoC motions in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions.

To evaluate the slice modeling technique, a full-length box model was developed with a simplified OoC which is an arch-like tissue asymmetrical in the radial direction and has a fluid tunnel within as shown in Figure 1a. With such a minimum representation of the OoC, a full-length box model was solvable computationally, and at the same time, the asymmetry and the fluid tunnel could potentially create intricate motions in the transverse, radial, and longitudinal directions. A slice model corresponding to about 75% distance from the base of the full-length model shown in Fig. 1b was developed. This location was chosen because of the availability of measured data at that location¹. The comparison of the results between the full-length and slice model provides insight into the capability, accuracy, and limitations of the slice model in capturing the 3D micromechanics of OoC.

Since there is no stapes input location, another important question that arises is how the slice model should be stimulated. Three different stimulation methods for the slice model were tested, namely, pressure stimulation on the

bottom wall of the scala tympani (ST), on the top wall of the scala vestibuli (SV), or on both ST and SV walls. The results from the full-length and slice models were compared, and it was found that the slice model with Floquet BCs with any of the stimulation methods could reproduce the results of the micromechanics of the simplified OoC in the transverse, radial, and longitudinal directions at various frequencies within a small error. In addition, results from the slice model with wavenumber that was three times higher or lower than the baseline wavenumber were compared. Not surprisingly, applying a continuity BC where the two faces of the slice have the same phase (instead of Floquet BC) failed to capture longitudinal motion in the OoC. These findings demonstrate the necessity for 3D FE models using Floquet BCs with the correct wavenumber-frequency relationship to capture the 3D motion within the OoC.

METHODS

A full-length box model for the mouse cochlea and a corresponding slice model at a location about 75% from the base near the apex were developed. For the full-length box model, the geometry and material properties of the BM and the OoC varied tonotopically as shown in Table 1. The BM was modeled as orthotropic elastic material, while for simplicity, OoC was modeled as an isotropic elastic material. The geometry of the BM^{12,13} and the young's modulus of the BM and the OoC^{14,15} were based on previous literature and further tuned to fit the passive best frequency map by Muller et al. 2005¹⁶ and Nankali et al. 2022¹⁷ as shown in Fig. (1e). The motion was stimulated by applying an input velocity of 0.1 mm/s at the oval window (represented by a square in Fig. 1a for simplicity for meshing.) The magnitude and phase of the traveling wave gain (nm/Pa at ear canal) along the length of the box model are shown in Fig. (1c). To translate the level of stimulation into ear canal (EC) pressure to compare with experimental data at a location near apex, data on mouse middle ear velocity was used¹⁸. The longitudinal location that fits the experimental data measured with OCT in Dewey et al. 2021 was at 4.6 mm (about 75% from base) and is shown in Fig. (1d). The best frequency at this location is about 6 kHz.

FIGURE 1. (a) Full-length box model for mouse cochlea. Black dotted vertical line indicates longitudinal (y) location of 4.6 mm (about 75% from base). (b) Cross-sectional view showing the minimum representation of OoC at $y = 4.6$ mm. (c) Transverse displacement magnitude in dB re nm/Pa at ear canal (EC) (upper panel) and phase in cycles (lower panel) at different frequencies along the length of the cochlea. 0.1 mm/s velocity stimulation was applied at the oval window. This was translated to EC pressure using middle ear data from Dong et al. 2014¹⁸. (d) Experimental data in blue and modelling results in orange at $y = 4.6$ mm. (e) Frequency-to-place map: from Muller et al. 2005¹⁶ based on neural data in blue; the Muller map shifted half-an-octave downward for hypothesized post-mortem case in orange¹⁹; Nankali et al. 2022¹⁷ based on OCT BM data at 80 dB SPL in green, which is closer to hypothesized post-mortem map; modelling results in red. (f) Real part of the wavenumber calculated from the full-

length model phase roll-off at $y = 4.6$ mm at different stimulation frequencies. (g) pressure difference between the two points, one right above OoC one right below BM, at $y = 4.6$ mm (shown in 1b as blue dots).

TABLE 1. Geometry and material properties of the full-length model. Linear interpolation was used between longitudinal locations.

Longitudinal location ($L_{BM} = 5.8$ mm)	0	$L_{BM}/3$	$L_{BM}^*3/5$	L_{BM}
BM width	64 μm	-	-	118 μm
BM thickness	14 μm	-	-	4.8 μm
$E_{BM, \text{radial}}$	18 MPa	3.5 MPa	3.2 MPa	1 MPa
$E_{BM, \text{long. and trans.}}$	1.5 MPa	0.9 MPa	0.8 MPa	0.4 MPa
E_{OoC}	0.05 MPa	0.0143 MPa	0.0125 MPa	0.01 MPa
$\nu_{BM, \nu_{OoC}}$			0.4	
$G_{BM, \text{all directions}}$		$E_{BM, \text{long. and trans.}}/2/(1+\nu_{BM})$		
BM damping loss factor			5%	
OoC damping loss factor			5%	

A slice model at the longitudinal location of 4.6 mm (about 75% from the base) was created, with a width of 29 μm , which is the width of the mesh in the longitudinal direction for the box model (Fig. 2a). As indicated in Figure 2b, the Floquet boundary condition enforces that the displacement (u) in the solid and the pressure (p) in the fluid at any given point (x, y, z) will follow the wave equation in the longitudinal (y) direction with the prescribed wavenumber (k). To apply Floquet BCs, the wavenumber-frequency relationship (k - f relationship) needs to be provided as an input. It is shown that k - f relationship only depends on the properties of the slice locally, and can be obtained by calculating the effective stiffness of the slice²⁰⁻²². For the current study, the k - f relationship was calculated from the phase response of the full-length model (Fig. 1f) at the corresponding location. The OoC was stimulated by applying pressure at the top of the SV wall, or on the bottom of the ST wall, or at both locations but with opposite signs. Note that these stimulation methods do not directly correlate to the pressure or velocity applied at the stapes. Therefore, to compare with the full-length box model results quantitatively, the pressure difference between points above the OoC and below the BM (as marked in Fig. 1b) were used as the common indicator for pressure level. The target pressure difference was obtained from the full-length model (Fig. 1g), while the pressure applied in the slice model were linearly adjusted to match the pressure difference in the full-length model. The stimulation frequencies were chosen to be up to 7 kHz because in the full-length model, the BM motion beyond 7 kHz was close to zero.

FIGURE 2. (a) Slice model at $y = 4.6$ mm ($\sim 75\%$ from the base). (b) Schematic of the slice on the y - z (longitudinal-transverse) planes with Floquet BC equations. For this slice, Δy was 29 μm , spanning approximately 4 hair cells.

RESULTS

Transverse, Radial, and Longitudinal Motion of the BM and OoC

The results of the full-length box model at about 75% from the base and the results of the slice model based on the geometry and material properties of the full-length model at the same location are shown in Fig 3. The color maps of the displacement field in all three directions are plotted for 4 (left panels) and 6 kHz (right panels) stimulations, with magnitude shown on the top panels and phase on the bottom. The stimulation method for this case is pressure at the top and bottom of the SV and the ST walls. For displacement magnitude at 6 kHz, the average absolute percentage

difference between the full-length and slice model results pixel-wise (not including pixels less than 0.18 nm magnitude of motion), was 0.8%, 2.5%, 24.1% for the transverse, radial, and longitudinal motion respectively (0.5%, 3.3%, and 6.9% for the three directions with ST only stimulation, 1.6%, 2.4%, and 40.8% for SV only stimulation). For displacement phase at 6 kHz, the average absolute differences pixel-wise was below 0.08 cycle in all three directions and for all three different stimulation methods. At 4 kHz, these differences were in the similar range.

FIGURE 3. The displacement in the transverse, radial, and longitudinal directions are shown by the rows for each sub panel. Within each row, left plots shows the full-length model and right plots show the slice model. Results for 4 kHz are shown the left column and for 6 kHz on the right column. The top row shows the magnitude in nm, while the bottom row shows the cyclic phase. Results shown for SV and ST pressure stimulation.

To quantify motion differences across frequencies, displacement magnitude in the transverse-, radial- and longitudinal- directions are plotted against stimulation frequencies in Figure 4 (a-c), from single point locations on the BM and on the OoC at locations indicated in Fig. 4d. Results from three different stimulation methods, namely pressure stimulation on both SV and ST walls, pressures on ST wall only, and SV wall only, show very little differences. This was expected but we wanted to check to be sure.

FIGURE 4. a-c) Displacement magnitude at a point on the BM and at a point in the OoC in the transverse-, radial-, and longitudinal-direction motions respectively at different stimulation frequencies. Results for full-length model in blue, and for slice model with three different stimulation methods in orange, green, and purple respectively. d) Diagram indicating the location of the points on the BM and in the OoC.

Different k - f Relationships for Floquet BC and Continuity BC

To test the effect of wavenumber-frequency functions on the motion patterns of the OoC and BM in the slice model, different k - f relationships were tested. For simplicity, while keeping its original shape, the k - f relationship in Figure 1f was reduced to one third ($k/3$), as well as doubled ($2*k$) and tripled ($3*k$). Results using these three different new k - f relationships are compared to the results from full-length model in Figure 5. Increasing the wavenumber (effectively shortening the wavelength) has more significant influence on the motion in all three directions of both BM and OoC. Lowering the wavenumber (increasing the wavelength) has less effect on the transverse and radial direction motions, but significantly lowered the longitudinal motion. Lastly, continuity BC was also tested. The result of continuity BC had no longitudinal motion, and similar transverse and radial direction motion as with the case of $k/3$ (longer wavelength).

FIGURE 5. Displacement magnitude at points on the BM and in the OoC in the transverse- (a), radial- (b), and longitudinal-directions (c) motion respectively at different stimulation frequencies. Results for full-length model in blue, and for slice model with three different k - f relationships in orange, green, and purple respectively. Diagram indicating the location of the points on BM and OoC are shown in Figure 4d.

DISCUSSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Current study shows that a slice cochlea model with Floquet BC can simulate the motion of the OoC and the BM quantitatively in all three directions below, at, and near BF. At frequencies higher than the BF, the motion in the longitudinal location was underestimated (Fig. 4c). The colormaps in Figure 3 shows that the slice model was able to capture the pattern of the motion accurately. It is worth noting that the location of the maximum displacement in the radial direction shifted from the left to the right of arch of the OoC when stimulation frequency changed from 4 to 6 kHz in both full-length and slice model. The one caveat is that we used a very simplified representation for the OoC as an asymmetric tissue with a tunnel in the middle.

Figure 5 with results from different k - f relationships shows that increasing the wavenumber has a significant effect qualitatively in the radial and longitudinal directions, changing the maximum displacement frequency in those directions. Although there is less effect on transverse motion in terms of BF, for the case with 3x wavenumber at 7 kHz, the relative motion between OoC and BM in the transverse direction flipped, with OoC motion being larger than the BM motion. Lowering the wavenumber decreased the longitudinal motion. For continuity BC, the behavior is like lowering the wavenumber to close to zero where the wavelength becomes infinite. As expected, this produces zero longitudinal motion. In summary, an accurate estimate of the wavenumber is important in capturing the 3D motion pattern in the slice model representation of the OoC.

It is worth noting that the thickness of the slice was 29 μm which indicates that the upper limit of wavenumber to avoid aliasing is about 8.6 cycles/mm (1 mm/(29 μm *4)). The highest wavenumber tested, 4.6 cycles/mm, which is 3 times the wavenumber at 7 kHz, was safely below this upper limit.

Among the three directions, the largest effect with different k - f relationships and continuity BC appeared to be in the longitudinal direction motion. This finding is not completely surprising because Floquet BC is unique in that it is able to capture the local effect of the longitudinal traveling wave. We hypothesize that the minimal effects on the transverse and radial directions may be due to the simplicity of the minimum representation of the OoC. The simplicity of it, perhaps, did not allow more complex modes to be excited, resulting similar results across different k - f relationships and continuity BC.

In conclusion, a 3D slice model of the cochlea with Floquet BCs provides a promising technology to study the micromechanics of the OoC in all three dimensions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by grant R01 DC007910 from the NIDCD of the NIH. We also thank the generous help offered by Andrew Tubelli and Gabriel Alberts on COMSOL Multiphysics, and John J. Guinan for his input.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Alessandro, Altoe]: When you have Floquet boundary condition, could you capture power changes across the slice, and could you put the imaginary part in the wavenumber.

[Yanli, Wang]: The slice model is not to capture the traveling wave, and I think for the thin slice, only the real part of the wavenumber can be determined by the local material property. For the imaginary part of the wavenumber, we need to whole box. We need to know what is happening before and after the slice. I in fact did a finite element experiment where I had multiple different boxes with different shapes, but they all have one location where they have the same geometry and material properties at that location. The real part of the wavenumber turned out to be the same with these different boxes, but the magnitudes were drastically different – which is basically the imaginary part of the wavenumber. I don't think we can know the imaginary part of the wavenumber from a slice.

[Julien, Meaud]: You don't include imaginary part, but you could test it right? Would it change your results? Second question, how about pressure distribution.

[Yanli, Wang]: For the pressure distribution, I have a backup slide here, and yes, the box and slice model have similar pressure distributions. For the imaginary part of the wavenumber, yes, I could extract the imaginary part from the box model and feed it back to the slice model, but since I believe that we can't extract the imaginary part just based on a thin slice, I don't know how meaningful that is.

[George, Samaras]: Hi Yanli, Great work. I have a few comments/questions:

1.) To my understanding, this model is passive, which would correspond most closely to a postmortem condition. While pressure focusing near the peak is most pronounced in an active condition, there is still some pressure focusing in the passive case arising from the mechanics, such that it is ambiguous whether $kH \ll 1$ is satisfied near your peak frequency of 6 kHz. From figure 1f, $k = 1$ cycle/mm at 6 kHz and the height of the duct is 0.4 mm, such that kH is not much smaller than 1. In line with Dr. Sisto's comment, a different stimulus could be considered to account for this (or to show that the effect of pressure focusing is relatively small for the passive case). Do you have future plans to look at active mechanics with this model, perhaps by using wavenumbers to represent the active pressure field and how that affects the mechanical predictions?

2.) In figure 4, you show that BM moves more than OoC. How does this compare to postmortem measurements of the OoC, such as those in Ren 2018 (for instance)? A direct comparison would be useful in testing the predictive ability of your model.

3.) Your comparison of continuity BC to Floquet BC, which shows that the effect of the traveling wave (represented by Floquet but neglected in continuity) is critical in predicting longitudinal motion. This is important to keep in mind for modelers and a very nice result of this work.

4.) Related to #3, you show that reducing the wavenumber (i.e. increasing the wavelength) lowers the longitudinal motion. Increased wavenumber means a smaller phase difference between the front and back of your slice, such that in effect, a very large wavelength corresponds to the continuity BC. Does this imply that in the long-wave tail region of the traveling wave, there is little to no longitudinal motion, but that longitudinal motion becomes much larger in the short-wave peak region?

5.) I think that the Meenderink and Dong 2022 paper on longitudinal motion should be referenced.

Overall this work provides some great insights on the relationship between wavenumber and longitudinal motion of the OoC.

[Yanli, Wang]: Thanks George for your questions and comments!

1. We do indeed have pressure focusing. We will show pressure distribution in a fuller manuscript. We could apply the pressure closer to the OoC indeed. When it gets too close, it starts to interfere with the natural pressure distribution around the OoC. Exactly how much or how less interference is good enough is subjective. For now, stimulating far away seems to make negligible impact on the pressure distribution around OoC, and thus similar to the displacement distribution on OoC. We will make this point clearer in final submission.

2. We don't claim that our extremely simplified OoC represents physiological OoC well, and so do not have the aim to meet the experimental data either. Our extremely simplified OoC only serves the purpose so that we can validate the slice model. We will make this point clearer in final submission.

3. Thank you!! We will emphasize this in our final submission!

4. Well said! Thank you and will do!

Thank you again for your comments that definitely make the manuscript stronger. We appreciate your read and feedback very much. :)

[Renata, Sisto]: I imagine the objective of the paper is comparing a full length transmission line cochlear model solved with the FEM technique to the slice model, solved by the FEM as well. The idea, if I understood, is to use the slice model to studying in much more detail the motion of the different part of the Organ of Corti.

The comparison is made between two passive models. Is that correct? I imagine that in solving the full length model the viscosity was set to zero as the model is passive and the viscous dissipation would grow rapidly with the wavenumber.

Could you clarify this point? I noticed that the gain factors in the full length model are very low (of the order of 10 dB). As the model is passive I can understand that but the gain in the case of the slice model are further reduced.

In figure 5 you show the transverse motion of the BM and the OcO in linear units and the growth at the peak is really very small. I can conclude that the response is not peaked at all. You insert some comments about that as you conclude that the BC you use make the model sensitive to the motion in the longitudinal direction but I think that some critical features of the traveling wave is lost in your approach.

You say that you stimulate the slice by applying pressure at the top of SV or at the bottom of ST or at both locations with different sign. With this strategy you assume that you are in the long wave limit or in other words in the limit $kH \ll 1$ (the wavelength greater than the height). In the long wave limit the pressure is uniformly distributed along the vertical direction but if you are modeling the short wave region you have to keep into account the fluid pressure focusing. The pressure, in the peak region, is maximum very close to the BM and has an exponentially decaying profile as you move vertically. You should apply the pressure very close to the BM, immediately above and below it, as the fluid, involved in the TW, has an effective height of the order of the wavelength. I would suggest to use this strategy to improve the model.

[Yanli, Wang]: Hi Renata, Thank you for your questions and comments! Your understanding of the objective of the model is right on. Thanks! :)

As to viscosity, we do have viscosity in the fluid, so the viscous loss is taking into account. In terms of gain factor, a better figure to look at is Figure 1 panel c and d, where the input of the stimulation is translated to be in reference of Ear Canal pressure using the middle ear transfer function measured by Dong et al. 2014. Comparing with experimental

data in Fig 1d, our gain factor is about right. For the rest of the figures, the stimulation level was 0.1 mm/s velocity stimulation at the oval window for all frequencies, so it is not constant dB SPL at EC across frequencies which is the reference we are more familiar with.

We try to present raw results with less layer of processing, so decided to keep 0.1 mm/s at the oval window instead of translating it into dB SPL at EC when presenting the rest of results where we do not need to compare with experimental data in dB SPL at EC.

There is indeed a pressure focusing right above the BM as well as OoC. For page limit, we didn't present figures of pressure distribution, and we will in a fuller manuscript.

Having the prescribed uniform pressure stimulation being too close to the OoC will actually interrupt the natural pressure distribution around the OoC.

The pressure applied on the next (imaginary) slice will have a phase shift to the pressure on this slice, so you are right if the wavenumber is too big, i.e. wavelength very short (say less than 8 times of the width of the slice), it may not be a good approximation. Otherwise, it would just be a piecewise approximation of a sine wave for the pressure applied. The validation procedure basically showed this as the error for 7 kHz, passing the best frequency with a higher wavenumber, is larger than it of lower frequencies (in the longitudinal direction at least). We showed that with a passive model, the width we chose is suitable for the wavenumber (or wavelength) we are looking at around the best frequency.

Hope that this all makes sense. Thank you again for your wonderful questions. We will make these points clearer in our final submission, and these definitely make our manuscript a stronger manuscript! Thanks again.